

Supply chain

Rare earths + precious metals mining

Material costs

Subsidy

Waste

Production

8 DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH

Health

3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

Data transmission

Content moderation

Fake news

Search engine

Click Worker

Cloud

3 GOOD HEALTH
AND WELL-BEING

Doom Scrolling

7 AFFORDABLE AND
CLEAN ENERGY

6 CLEAN WATER
AND SANITATION

12 RESPONSIBLE
CONSUMPTION
AND PRODUCTION

9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION
AND INFRASTRUCTURE

12 RESPONSIBLE
CONSUMPTION
AND PRODUCTION

AI assistant

6 CLEAN WATER
AND SANITATION

15 LIFE
ON LAND

Influencer Economy

3 GOOD HEALTH
AND WELL-BEING

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CONSUMPTION
AND PRODUCTION

9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION
AND INFRASTRUCTURE

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AND SANITATION

